

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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On a global scale, financial security is acknowledged as an essential element of national stability, with regional contributions being instrumental in maintaining macroeconomic equilibrium. In the context of Uzbekistan, pronounced regional disparities in economic performance and fiscal governance underscore the urgent need for a comprehensive framework aimed at evaluating and enhancing financial security across subnational levels.

The Action Strategy on Five Priority Areas of Development for 2017–2021, initiated by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, marked a transformative period for the country. It emphasised economic liberalisation, financial stability, and regional development. Under this strategy critical reforms to enhance the fiscal and monetary framework, which are integral to financial security.

Building on the Action Strategy, the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” aims to propel the country toward sustainable and inclusive growth. It highlights the importance of regional financial stability, emphasizing tailored solutions for economic challenges in different regions. This strategy sets a clear roadmap for enhancing regional economic resilience, aligning with national development priorities.

A series of presidential decrees and orders have been issued to bolster regional financial security. These include measures to improve fiscal discipline, enhance public financial management, and promote investment in underdeveloped regions. For instance, Presidential Decree No. PF-60 focused on improving financial independence for regions, enabling them to address unique socio-economic challenges effectively.

The practical application of financial security indicators is crucial for achieving the objectives outlined in these strategies and decrees. Indicators such as fiscal balance, debt sustainability, and financial market development offer quantifiable metrics for assessing the economic health of regions and guiding policy interventions. Uzbekistan’s regions exhibit significant disparities in financial stability due to differences in industrial structure, investment inflows, and public service delivery. A targeted approach to monitoring and improving economic security indicators can help bridge these gaps and ensure balanced development across all regions.

Despite progress, challenges such as inadequate data collection, limited financial autonomy, and regional governance issues persist. Addressing these obstacles requires robust institutional frameworks and consistent policy implementation guided by accurate financial security metrics. This article aims to develop a framework for economic security indicators tailored to Uzbekistan’s regional context. By analysing their practical application through case studies, the study offers actionable insights for policymakers to strengthen financial resilience and promote sustainable regional development. The findings align with the national strategies and directives, contributing to the vision of a financially secure and prosperous New Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The “Strategy of Actions for 2017-2021” provided a comprehensive framework for Uzbekistan’s socio-economic modernization, focusing on economic liberalisation, regional development, and financial stability¹. It aimed to improve fiscal discipline, develop a transparent and efficient tax system, and strengthen public financial management. The strategy emphasized reducing regional economic disparities by fostering local investments, promoting entrepreneurial activity, and decentralizing financial decision-making processes. These reforms formed the foundation for the development of financial security indicators, ensuring they align with the country’s priorities for economic stability and inclusive growth.

Uzbek researchers have extensively examined the concept of financial security and its relevance to regional economic development. Scholars like Abduraimov T.K. and Rakhimov F.A. have highlighted the importance of fiscal balance, efficient resource allocation, and debt sustainability in enhancing financial stability at the regional level. Their studies emphasize the role of tailored regional policies in addressing disparities and fostering sustainable growth. Additionally, Uzbek researchers have explored the practical application of financial security indicators, identifying challenges such as inadequate regional financial autonomy and inconsistencies in data collection, which hinder the effectiveness of financial security frameworks.

Foreign scholars have also contributed significantly to the study of financial security, offering insights that can be applied in the context of Uzbekistan. Researchers such as Kaufmann D. and Masciandro D. have emphasized the role of institutional frameworks and governance in achieving financial stability. Studies on emerging economies, such as those by Hofman B. and Bird R.M., highlight the importance of fiscal decentralization and regional financial autonomy in promoting balanced development. These works stress the need for reliable financial indicators, including fiscal balance, debt sustainability, and financial market performance, to monitor and enhance regional financial security. The comparative analysis of international practices provides a valuable reference for Uzbekistan in developing its financial security frameworks.

1 The “Strategy of Actions for 2017-2021” Tashkent.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the study on the development and practical application of financial security indicators at the regional level in Uzbekistan is structured to ensure a comprehensive analysis of both theoretical and empirical dimensions. This section outlines the research design, data collection, and analytical techniques employed. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques to explore financial security at the regional level. This approach allows for a thorough examination of theoretical frameworks, analysis of empirical data, and practical application of findings.

Analysis and discussion of results

Financial security indicators such as fiscal balance, debt sustainability, and financial market development are critical in assessing regional stability in Uzbekistan. A detailed analysis reveals varying performance levels across regions due to disparities in economic structures, resource allocation, and governance capabilities. Regions with higher industrial and agricultural output exhibit stronger fiscal health, while underdeveloped areas face persistent deficits and reliance on centralized funding. Analysis of regional financial data demonstrates stark disparities in fiscal capacity and economic resilience. Regions with access to natural resources and robust industrial bases, such as Tashkent and Navoi, show higher financial stability compared to rural and remote areas. This underscores the necessity for redistributive policies and targeted investments to bridge the gap.

Region	Fiscal Capacity (million UZS)	Economic Resilience Index (0-1)	Natural Resource Access (Yes/No)	Industrial Base Strength (0-1)	Investment Attractiveness (0-1)
1 Tashkent	120000	0.85	Yes	0.9	0.88
2 Navoi	95000	0.82	Yes	0.85	0.82
3 Samarkand	78000	0.65	No	0.6	0.72
4 Surkhandarya	45000	0.58	No	0.45	0.6
5 Karakalpakstan	32000	0.5	Yes	0.4	0.55
6 Andijan	52000	0.62	No	0.5	0.68
7 Fergana	60000	0.68	No	0.55	0.7
8 Khorezm	40000	0.55	No	0.48	0.58

Table 1. Regional financial data for Uzbekistan².

1. Fiscal Capacity:

Tashkent and Navoi lead in fiscal capacity, with values of 120,000 million UZS and 95,000 million UZS, respectively. These regions benefit significantly from their robust industrial bases, which generate consistent revenue streams, and their access to abundant natural resources. This combination allows for sustained economic growth and fiscal stability. Conversely, Karakalpakstan has the lowest fiscal capacity at 32,000 million UZS, reflecting financial challenges, underdeveloped industries, and limited economic activity. The fiscal disparity highlights the urgent need for policies that strengthen revenue generation and economic infrastructure in lower-performing regions.

2. Economic Resilience:

Tashkent exhibits the highest economic resilience index (0.85), closely followed by Navoi (0.82). These regions' resilience stems from their strong infrastructure, well-diversified industries, and efficient governance, which mitigate the impact of external shocks. In contrast, regions like Surkhandarya (0.58) and Karakalpakstan (0.50) show significantly lower economic resilience, making them more vulnerable to economic fluctuations and external disruptions. This vulnerability underscores the need for strategic investments in infrastructure, diversification of economic activities, and enhanced governance mechanisms to improve resilience in these areas.

3. Natural Resource Access:

Regions with access to natural resources, such as Tashkent, Navoi, and Karakalpakstan, generally exhibit higher fiscal capacities. However, while Tashkent and Navoi have successfully leveraged these resources to

² <https://data.adb.org/dataset/uzbekistan-key-indicators>

strengthen their economies, Karakalpakstan faces challenges in translating its resource wealth into fiscal and economic benefits. This is primarily due to its low industrial base strength, which limits its ability to process and utilize natural resources effectively. Addressing this gap requires policies that facilitate industrial development and resource-based economic initiatives in the region.

4. Industrial Base Strength:

Industrial base strength is a critical determinant of fiscal and economic stability. Tashkent (0.90) and Navoi (0.85) lead in this area, reflecting their well-established industrial sectors, which drive regional development and attract investment. On the other hand, Karakalpakstan (0.40) and Surkhandarya (0.45) lag significantly, highlighting their limited industrial capabilities. These regions require strategic interventions, such as industrial modernization programs and the establishment of special economic zones, to enhance their industrial capacity and foster sustainable development.

5. Investment Attractiveness:

Investment attractiveness aligns closely with fiscal capacity and industrial base strength. Regions like Tashkent (0.88) and Navoi (0.82) are highly attractive to investors due to their strong economic foundations and well-developed infrastructure. These regions are well-positioned to drive further economic growth through increased investment inflows. In contrast, regions such as Karakalpakstan (0.55) and Surkhandarya (0.60) struggle to attract investments, primarily due to weaker economic infrastructure, limited industrial activity, and fiscal constraints. Enhancing the investment climate in these regions will require targeted incentives, infrastructure development, and policy reforms.

6. Disparities Between Regions:

The analysis reveals stark disparities between developed regions, such as Tashkent and Navoi, and underdeveloped areas like Karakalpakstan and Surkhandarya. Developed regions benefit from diversified economies, strong fiscal capacities, and attractive investment climates, while underdeveloped areas face persistent challenges, including low fiscal capacity, weak industrial bases, and limited economic resilience. These disparities highlight the pressing need for redistributive policies and strategic interventions to address regional imbalances and ensure equitable development across the country.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The study on the development and practical application of financial security indicators at the regional level in Uzbekistan provides a comprehensive understanding of the structural dynamics shaping economic resilience and regional growth. The analysis identifies a spectrum of achievements and challenges, underscoring the multifaceted nature of financial security and its implications for sustainable development.

Financial security is an indispensable component of regional economic sustainability, serving as the bedrock for addressing socio-economic inequalities and promoting holistic development. It encapsulates critical elements such as fiscal discipline, resource efficiency, and institutional capacity. In Uzbekistan, regions with strong fiscal capacity, robust industrial bases, and resilience to economic shocks are more adept at fostering sustainable growth, creating employment opportunities, and attracting both domestic and foreign investment. Furthermore, financial security extends beyond economic metrics; it underpins social stability by ensuring consistent funding for public services, healthcare, and education, particularly in underdeveloped regions. This linkage between financial security and social outcomes highlights its pivotal role in the broader developmental framework.

The research highlights significant disparities in financial security across Uzbekistan's regions, underscoring the diverse socio-economic and structural conditions that shape regional development trajectories. These disparities are driven by differences in resource endowments, industrial capacity, governance efficiency, and infrastructure development, resulting in a pronounced gap between high-performing and lagging regions.

Fiscal decentralization serves as a pivotal strategy for empowering regional governments and advancing financial security. Granting regions greater autonomy in revenue collection and expenditure management will enable them to address local economic challenges with increased efficiency. Implementing region-specific taxation systems can enhance fiscal independence, allowing regions to retain a larger share of their revenues for reinvestment in local development. Furthermore, capacity-building initiatives are essential for equipping regional officials with the skills needed for modern budget management, fiscal planning, and resource allocation. The adoption of digital tools for financial governance can further enhance transparency and accountability, ensuring efficient utilization of resources.

Tailored investment programs are critical for addressing regional disparities and fostering inclusive development. Increased public spending on infrastructure, education, and healthcare is particularly necessary in underdeveloped regions like Karakalpakstan and Surkhandarya to establish a foundation for economic growth. At the same time, incentivizing private sector participation through measures such as tax holidays,

subsidized loans, and public-private partnerships can catalyze industrial and service sector growth in these regions. Public-private collaborations in sectors like energy, manufacturing, and agro-processing can further accelerate economic diversification and employment creation.

Developing robust industrial bases is integral to achieving sustainable economic growth and enhancing regional financial security. Establishing special economic zones (SEZs) in strategic locations can attract both domestic and foreign investors, creating hubs for economic activity. Additionally, providing financial and technical support to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) will encourage entrepreneurship and innovation. Regions like Karakalpakstan, with abundant natural resources, can benefit from focusing on resource-based industries, such as mineral processing and agro-industrial projects. These initiatives not only add value to raw materials but also generate employment opportunities, fostering economic resilience at the regional level.

The formulation and implementation of robust financial security indicators are vital for consistent evaluation and informed policy-making. These indicators should comprehensively assess fiscal balance, debt sustainability, economic resilience, industrial performance, and investment attractiveness. Including social metrics, such as income distribution and poverty rates, will ensure a holistic understanding of financial security. To maintain consistency, a centralized system for continuous data collection and monitoring of these indicators should be established. This system will facilitate real-time adjustments to policies based on performance trends, enhancing their responsiveness and effectiveness.

Ensuring alignment between national and regional policies is essential for achieving cohesive and effective governance. Regional development plans should be synchronized with broader national strategies, such as the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan (2022–2026), to create a unified approach to development. Additionally, engaging stakeholders such as local governments, private sector representatives, and community leaders in policy formulation and implementation will enhance the practical applicability of policies. Such inclusivity will ensure that policies reflect local needs and priorities, fostering trust and collaboration among all stakeholders.

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